

THE ROLE OF S-COMMERCE IN HIGHER EDUCATION: ANALYZING THE PRESENCE OF SERBIAN FACULTIES ON TIKTOK

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Abstract: *TikTok, as a key tool of S-Commerce, offers new opportunities for promotion and interaction in higher education. An analysis of the presence of state faculties in Serbia on TikTok reveals that only 18% of the 89 faculties have official accounts, with the University of Belgrade leading with nine active profiles. The results highlight a significant untapped potential of this platform. A strategic approach and exchange of best practices are proposed to enhance digital presence, improve visibility, and foster deeper connections with younger generations..*

Keywords: *S-Commerce, TikTok, higher education, social networks, promotion.*

1. INTRODUCTION

The integration of social media into commerce, commonly referred to as social commerce (*S-Commerce*), has become increasingly relevant in higher education marketing. Platforms such as TikTok offer new opportunities for universities to enhance visibility, engage prospective students and build meaningful connections with digital native audiences.

S-Commerce merges social interaction with commercial activity, enabling institutions to communicate directly with users and foster engagement through content-driven strategies (Hajli, 2015). TikTok in particular, has rapidly emerged as a high-engagement platform due to its short-form video format and viral potential (Influencer Marketing Hub, 2024). While originally perceived as an entertainment-focused app, it is now being adopted by various organizations, including educational institutions, as a tool to reach younger demographics.

Despite the widespread use of social media in higher education marketing, TikTok remains a relatively underexplored channel in academic research (Wang & Herrando, 2019). This paper aims to provide a focused literature review on the application of S-Commerce in promoting higher education institutions (HEIs), followed by an analysis of TikTok presence among faculties within Serbian universities, examining its potential through the lens of S-Commerce principles.

2. S-COMMERCE: THEORETICAL BACKGROUND

The concept of social commerce (*S-commerce*) represents a distinct form of electronic commerce that incorporates elements of social interaction into the purchasing process. Rather than serving as passive content consumers, users of social media platforms actively shape demand by commenting, sharing, and recommending products (Kaplan & Haenlein, 2010). At its core, S-Commerce leverages social networks as transactional environments, enabling dynamic, two-way communication between brands and consumers.

According to Zhang and Benyoucef (2016), S-Commerce integrates social components such as peer recommendations and content sharing with traditional e-commerce functions to deliver a more engaging and personalized user experience. It is distinguished from conventional e-commerce by three key dimensions: social interaction, commercial intent and user engagement. Social interaction forms the foundation of S-Commerce, fostering trust through user-generated reviews and social proof (Wang & Herrando, 2019). Hajli et al. (2017) also investigate the relationship between trust and purchase intentions in social networking sites, discovering that trust plays a substantial role in consumers' decisions to engage in S-commerce transactions.

Shin et al. (2020) delve into service quality management in S-commerce, analyzing how service design qualities affect consumer satisfaction and decision-making processes. Their research found that hedonic value surpasses utilitarian value in impacting user satisfaction and responsiveness towards social commerce service offerings. Hajli et al. (2017) also emphasize the significant role of social technologies in shaping interactions among consumers, businesses and organizations in the S-commerce landscape.

Platforms like TikTok and Instagram facilitate viral dissemination of product-related content through comments and shares (Huang & Benyoucef, 2013). „In 2025, sales through social networks accounted for an estimated 17.11 percent of total online sales” (Statista, 2025). Live commerce has grown in popularity in recent years. Its prevalence is only expected to increase as companies utilize livestreaming technologies more and more for promotional and marketing purposes. Digital shoppers benefit from live commerce because it offers attractive discounts as well as inspiration and ideas. In 2022, Facebook was the leading social network platform where internet users purchased products during live streaming events. As with social commerce, Asian countries have paved the way for this highly interactive shopping experience. In 2023, over seven in ten consumers engaged in live shopping in China, India, Thailand, and United Arab Emirates (Statista, 2025).

This comprehensive perspective underlines the collaborative essence of S-commerce, suggesting that successful strategies must integrate social and technological dimensions effectively.

3. THE ROLE OF S-COMMERCE IN HIGHER EDUCATION PROMOTION

S-Commerce is gaining prominence in the education sector, where it serves as a strategic tool for institutional promotion, student recruitment and audience engagement. By merging educational content with social media interactivity, universities can significantly enhance their visibility among younger demographics. The key applications of S-Commerce in higher education include:

- **Program Promotion:** Platforms such as TikTok, Instagram and Facebook allow institutions to creatively showcase academic programs, student life and campus activities. Short videos, interactive posts and visual storytelling foster familiarity and interest. TikTok, in particular, facilitates viral dissemination through lecture snippets, behind-the-scenes content and educational challenges (Influencer Marketing Hub, 2024).
- **Student Engagement:** S-Commerce enables real-time interaction with current and prospective students through comments, polls and live streams. Institutions utilize Instagram Live for Q&A sessions on admissions, while TikTok campaigns featuring student content creators enhance authenticity and deepen engagement (Huang & Benyoucef, 2013).
- **Educational Resource Sharing:** Universities increasingly use social platforms to distribute tutorials, academic tips and research highlights, contributing to educational accessibility and community outreach (Zhang & Benyoucef, 2016). This approach not only attracts students but also reframes the institutional role in public knowledge dissemination.
- **Brand Building:** Social media supports institutional branding by combining informative and entertaining content. Participation in viral trends allows universities to align with contemporary discourse and strengthen public perception (Stephen & Toubia, 2010).

As SproutSocial (2023) notes, “thanks to social media, every aspect of the college experience can be shared,” offering a level of transparency and interaction that traditional media cannot match. Recent data confirms the strategic value of social media in education. Around 68% of high school students use social platforms to research universities, underscoring the shift toward digital-first exploration (SproutSocial, 2023). Moreover, 80% of alumni organizations identify social media and digital content as key tools for maintaining alumni relations. Importantly, 41% of educational institutions report a direct link between their social media strategy and increased enrollment, highlighting its role as a core, not peripheral, element of modern marketing (SproutSocial, 2023).

Social Media Strategies Summit Blog (2024) identifies effective uses of TikTok in higher education marketing. The article “19 Great Examples of TikTok Content for Higher Education” outlines best practices:

- *Humanizing Leadership:* Harvard College features Dean Rakesh Khurana answering personal questions to create a more approachable image.
- *Trend Engagement:* Washington University in St. Louis leverages trending memes and challenges to connect with a wider audience.
- *Tradition Showcasing:* The University of Alabama shares viral time-lapse videos of students forming the university logo, reinforcing community and tradition.

- *Humor and Relatability*: The University of Michigan uses humor to align with TikTok’s entertainment-centric culture and appeal to Gen Z.

These strategies illustrate how TikTok can serve as a cost-effective, high-engagement tool for fostering authentic communication, strengthening institutional identity and reaching a digital-native audience.

A study by Escamilla-Fajardo et al. (2021) even explored the pedagogical value of TikTok in higher education by examining its integration into a corporal expression sport course. The research demonstrated that TikTok, when used as a learning tool, significantly enhanced student engagement, motivation and creativity. Students were not only more actively involved in the learning process but also developed essential digital competencies such as video editing and content creation.

The alignment of video content with promotional strategies is particularly relevant to platforms like TikTok, which have redefined social media interactions through short-form video content designed for virality and engagement (G.U. & F.O., 2023). According to Marešová et al., social media provides extensive feedback mechanisms that enable universities to tailor their marketing efforts effectively based on analytics gathered from user interactions (Marešová et al., 2020).

Furthermore, the literature suggests that universities can benefit from employing influencer marketing strategies on platforms such as TikTok. Successful collaborations between influencers and educational brands can yield better engagement metrics, as followers tend to trust influencer recommendations more than traditional advertisements (Ibáñez-Sánchez et al., 2021). Influencers can amplify the reach and authenticity of educational content, making it more relatable and appealing to prospective students.

Importantly, the impact of TikTok is also reflected in the motivational effects on students. Research has shown that engagement with TikTok can influence students' academic performance and learning motivation, with students perceiving social media presence as beneficial to their learning processes (Hill et al., 2024). Thus, as higher education institutions craft their marketing strategies, they must account for the multifaceted influences of TikTok, balancing promotional content with authentic engagement that resonates with students' realities and aspirations as they navigate their educational journeys (Qin et al., 2022).

4. THE ANALYSIS OF THE PRESENCE OF SERBIAN FACULTIES ON TIKTOK

According to the Ministry of Education of the Republic of Serbia, there are nine state universities, including the University of Belgrade, University of Novi Sad, University of Niš, University of Kragujevac, University of Arts in Belgrade, University of Defence, State University of Novi Pazar, University of Priština (temporarily located in Kosovska Mitrovica), and the University of Criminal Investigation and Police Studies (Ministarstvo prosvete, 2024). Additionally, Serbia has ten private universities (Edukacija, 2024). Given the differences in organization and funding models, this study focuses solely on state universities.

The analysis included all nine Serbian universities, specifically their constituent faculties. The research process was conducted during the December 2024, and involved the following steps:

- **TikTok Search**: Keywords included full faculty names and common abbreviations (e.g., “Fakultet tehničkih nauka Novi Sad” for the Faculty of Technical Sciences and “Ekof”, etc.) to identify official TikTok profiles.
- **Account Verification**: Identified accounts were examined to determine their official status by reviewing usernames, content and links to institutional websites.
- **Categorization**: Faculties were grouped into three categories: (1) those with official TikTok accounts, (2) those without any presence, and (3) those represented by student-generated informal content. Only faculties with verified official accounts were included in the analysis.
- **Content Analysis**: Official accounts, such as the Faculty of Fine Arts in Belgrade (@flubeograd), were assessed based on the type of content they published: informational, promotional or educational.

The University of Belgrade, the largest state university in Serbia, comprises 31 faculties, organized into four academic fields: social sciences and humanities, medical sciences, natural and mathematical sciences, and technical and technological sciences (University of Belgrade, 2024).

Table 1 presents the faculties of the University of Belgrade that maintain official TikTok accounts.

Table 1: Faculties of the University of Belgrade with Official TikTok Presence

The name of HEI	TikTok name	Content type
Faculty of Economics (Ekonomski fakultet)	@ekofbg	Informational, educational, promotional

<i>Faculty of Political Sciences</i> (Fakultet političkih nauka)	@fjn_beograd	Informational
<i>Faculty of Special Education and Rehabilitation</i> (Fakultet za specijalnu edukaciju i rehabilitaciju)	@parlamentfasper	Informational, educational
<i>Faculty of Philosophy</i> (Filozofski fakultet)	@filozofski_fakultet_bg	Informational
<i>Faculty of Physics</i> (Fizički fakultet)	@fizicki_fakultet	Educational
<i>Faculty of Civil Engineering</i> (Građevinski fakultet)	@gradjevnickifakultet	Informational
<i>Faculty of Chemistry</i> (Hemijski fakultet)	@hemijskifakultet	No content on the account
<i>Faculty of Transport and Traffic Engineering</i> (Saobraćajni fakultet)	@saobracajni_fakultet	Informational, educational, entertaining
<i>Faculty of Forestry</i> (Šumarski fakultet)	@sumarskifakultetbeograd	Informational, educational

The University of Novi Sad, founded in 1960, is one of the leading higher education institutions in Serbia and the region. The university consists of 14 faculties, which are located in four cities: Novi Sad, Subotica, Zrenjanin and Sombor. The faculties cover a wide range of disciplines, from natural and technical sciences to social and artistic fields, providing education to more than 50,000 students. (University of Novi Sad, 2024).

Table 2: Faculties of the University of Novi Sad with Official TikTok Presence

The name of HEI	The TikTok name	Content type
<i>Faculty of Agriculture</i> (Poljoprivredni fakultet, Novi Sad)	@poljo.ns	Informational, educational
<i>Faculty of Technical Sciences</i> (Fakultet tehničkih nauka, Novi Sad)	@ftn_ns	Informational, educational, entertaining
<i>Faculty of Civil Engineering</i> (Građevinski fakultet, Subotica)	@gfsbotica	Informational
<i>Faculty of Education</i> (Pedagoški fakultet, Sombor)	@pedagoski_fakultet_so	Informational, entertaining

The University of Niš was founded in 1965 and is one of the key higher education institutions in southeastern Serbia. The University stands out for its contribution to education, science and the development of the local community, and it has a total of 14 faculties. Faculties cover a wide range of scientific disciplines, including technical, natural-mathematical, social-humanistic, medical and artistic fields (Univerzitet u Nišu, 2024).

Table 3: Faculties of the University of Niš with Official TikTok Presence

The name of HEI	The TikTok name	Content type
<i>Faculty of Technology</i> (Tehnološki fakultet, Leskovac)	@tehnoloski.fakultet	Informational
<i>Faculty of Education</i> (Pedagoški fakultet, Vranje)	@pedagoski.fakultet	Informational

The University of Kragujevac, a state HEI established on May 21, 1976, traces its roots to the Lyceum of the Principality of Serbia founded in 1838, the first institution of higher education in modern Serbia (University of Kragujevac, 2024). Today, it comprises 12 faculties across six cities in central Serbia. A keyword-based search on TikTok revealed that none of these faculties maintain an official presence on the

platform. While individual users and students occasionally share related content, there are no verified institutional accounts.

The University of Arts in Belgrade, founded in 1957, is a key pillar of higher education in the arts in Serbia. It consists of four faculties covering music, visual and applied arts, and dramatic arts, including theater, film and television (University of Arts in Belgrade, 2024). Among its faculties, only the Faculty of Fine Arts (*Fakultet likovih umetnosti*) maintains an official TikTok account (@flubeograd), sharing informative content related to academic activities and programs.

In contrast, the research found no official TikTok accounts for the University of Defence in Belgrade, the State University of Novi Pazar, the University of Priština (temporarily based in Kosovska Mitrovica), or the University of Criminal Investigation and Police Studies.

5. DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION

The emergence of S-commerce in higher education marks a strategic shift toward more interactive, engaging and student-centered communication. TikTok, as one of the most popular platforms among younger audiences, offers a unique opportunity for universities to promote their programs, interact with prospective students, and build recognizable digital brands.

Recent studies (Marešová et al., 2020; Ibáñez-Sánchez et al., 2021; G.U. & F.O., 2023) highlight the multidimensional role of trust, user behavior, service quality and social interaction in shaping the effectiveness of S-commerce. These insights call for a deeper understanding of user dynamics on social platforms, not only in business but increasingly in educational contexts.

This study found that only 16 out of 89 public faculties in Serbia (approximately 18%) have official TikTok accounts. The University of Belgrade leads in digital presence, with nine faculties actively using the platform. These faculties, such as the Faculty of Economics, Faculty of Transport and Traffic Engineering and Faculty of Forestry, demonstrate a creative, strategic approach by producing diverse content types, ranging from informative and educational to promotional and entertaining.

In contrast, faculties from the Universities of Kragujevac, Novi Pazar and Priština have no official presence on TikTok, indicating a missed opportunity to reach and engage younger audiences. A similar situation was observed at the University of Arts in Belgrade, where only the Faculty of Fine Arts maintains a verified account. This isolated case of good practice highlights the untapped potential within other faculties at the same institution.

Faculties that are active on TikTok increase their visibility, enhance their digital footprint and attract new generations of students. Those that remain absent risk reduced competitiveness in the increasingly digital landscape of higher education.

These findings underscore the need for modernizing communication strategies in academia through the lens of S-Commerce. Based on the research results, the following recommendations are proposed:

- **Strategic content development:** Institutions should adopt tailored strategies that align with the logic of S-Commerce: short videos, interactive formats, educational challenges and engaging content suited to younger audiences.
- **Encouraging digital onboarding:** Faculties currently absent from TikTok should be supported in launching official accounts and building content that blends educational and entertaining elements.
- **Knowledge sharing:** Successful examples, such as the Faculty of Economics, University of Belgrade, and the Faculty of Technical Sciences, University of Novi Sad, should be used as benchmarks. Sharing best practices across institutions may accelerate digital transformation and effective use of social platforms.

By integrating traditional academic values with modern digital tools and S-Commerce principles, universities can significantly enhance their visibility, attract prospective students and strengthen connections with current ones. In summary, TikTok's integration into higher education offers more than just a communication tool, it fosters community, motivation and academic interest through culturally relevant content. This positions it as a powerful medium for educational marketing in the digital age.

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